

A STUDY ON VIRTUAL LEARNING AND ITS ACCEPTANCE BY YOUTH IN THANE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The spread of covid 19 across the globe has led to an unprecedented experiment in virtual learning education. “Virtual learning” typically refers to a course that is completely virtual. Learners receive instructional content, submit assignments, take tests, and interact entirely online, or virtual. This can happen “synchronously” (e.g., all learners joining a live session at the same time) or “asynchronously” (e.g., Learners logging in to do homework whenever they want). “Blended learning” refers to a course that mixes online learning and face-to-face learning together. Internet is now playing a bigger role in our lives and dictating how we live, socialize, teach, and learn. As the Internet is developing into a main educational tool, online education offers the educator and the learner access to numerous resources The number of online courses raise and change the way people learn. People used to study in a classroom with a tutor in front of them, but now people only need to sit in front of a screen to learn new things. Virtual learning is designed to reach and engaged the modern learner on one to one basis anywhere, anytime. However, the acceptance of virtual learning by youth is still questioned. This research paper consists of primary as well as secondary data. It studies the perception, impact of virtual learning and most importantly its acceptance by youth residing in Thane district.

Keywords: *Virtual Learning, Educational Tool, Youth*

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Introduction: -

Virtual learning is a learning experience that is enhanced through utilizing computers and/or

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the internet both outside and inside the facilities of the educational organization. The instruction most commonly takes place in an online environment. The teaching activities are carried out online whereby the teacher and learners are physically separated (in terms of place, time, or both). The quality of online education depends on the proper use of digital technologies in accordance with modern educational theories. Behaviorism examines how students behave while learning. It focuses on how learners respond to certain stimuli. When the teacher repeats the stimuli, they can observe, control, and modify the learner's individual behavior. Learners do what they are instructed to do and are only prepared to reproduce basic facts and automatically perform tasks. In virtual learning behaviorism can be applied through step-by-step video tutorials, game-based activities, regular and constructive feedback, quizzes, etc. Teaching and learning are explained as complex interactive social phenomena that take place between teachers and students. Learning activities focus on experience sharing, teamwork, and collaborative learning.

Literature Review

Urdan & Weggen (2000) related that technology, the rapid obsolescence of knowledge and training, the need for just-in-time training delivery, and the search for cost-effective ways to meet learning needs of a globally distributed workforce have redefined the processes that underlie design, development and delivery of training and education in the workplace.

Hall and Snider (2000) define e-learning as the process of learning via computers over the Internet and intranets. Hall and Snider extended that e-learning is also referred to as web-based training, online training, distributed learning or technology for learning.

Ronnie et al. (2020) found the unavailability of fast and reliable internet connection as a major concern than either device ownership or technical aptitude. Whereas difficulties to adjust to online learning platforms are also reported in the exiting literature.

Wong (2007) stated that one of the advantages of e-learning is that it provides time flexibility, which can be detrimental to the learner since intrinsic motivation and self-consciousness are required to the maximum. He has defined e-learning as the activities of teach based on computers their networks and usage of multi-media technologies. E-learning is the adoption of various electronic devices for learning purposes via electronic media.

Objectives of Study

1. To study the perception and behaviour of learners towards virtual learning
2. To analyse the impact of virtual learning on its learners
3. To understand the acceptance level of virtual learning
4. To compare the learner's preference towards online or offline learning

Limitations

1. Study restricted to only 50 respondents
2. Time frame was not sufficient for detailed analysis
3. All the answers given by respondent are assumed to be true

Research Methodology

The study was conducted in Thane District. Data was collected from primary as well as secondary sources. Different books and journals, websites were used for data collection. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire (Google form) 50 respondents filled the questionnaire.

Data Interpretation & Analysis

Figure 1.1 Source Sample Survey

From the above pie chart, it can be observed that majority of the people are distracted with various activities at home while learning virtually, also lot of them face challenges which are not suitable as per the situation and very few % of the people are comfortable with learning as per their own space.

I am prepared to learn to study in an Virtual Learning environment.

40 responses

Figure 1.2

From the above pie chart, it can be seen that 50% of the respondents are not sure about being prepared to learn in a virtual environment and 32.5% are not ready at all to study in virtual environment. This shows that respondents have not completely accepted the virtual learning environment

Given the current scenario due you feel virtual learning is the future ahead

40 responses

Figure 1.3

From the above pie chart, it is visible that people do not see virtual learning as a future ahead, majority of them are neutral about it and 30% have completely disagreed that virtual learning is the future ahead.

Is virtual learning more effective learning than traditional offline learning
40 responses

Figure 1.4

From the above chart it can be observed that virtual learning is still not as effective as traditional offline learning, 50% of respondents are not sure about it and 37.5% respondents firmly believe that traditional offline learning is more effective

What would be your preferred method of learning keeping in mind the current situation
40 responses

Figure 1.5

From the above pie chart, it can be seen that Blended learning is the need of an hour, majority of the learners are not sure about attending lectures completely online mode or completely

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offline mode, there needs to be a balance between the two, that is why blended approach is the suitable option in the current scenario.

Conclusion

Virtual learning not just a change of technology. It is part of a redefinition of how we transmit knowledge, skills, and values to younger generations of learners and students. Learners are still skeptical in adopting virtual learning as major source of education and courses. Traditional classrooms need to be modernized, but virtual schools are not necessarily the answer. Instead, they believe that traditional classrooms should incorporate more technology such as iPads, Smart Boards, and computers. Students need to be exposed to new technologies, but not at the risk of losing social interaction. Most learners need exposure to social interaction in order to succeed in today's society. They need to be able to interact with and communicate with coworkers, bosses, and customers. Unlike traditional schools, most virtual schools cannot provide this necessary interaction. Virtual learning environment requires better infrastructure for both teachers and learners. Blended approach can be the best possible situation keeping in mind the current scenario.

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